

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

Name

Student ID Number : P1-J0308211058XTO ECREPORT

Vocational School English Analysis (IKN-Sains)

Object;

Muhammad Iqbal Emirza Paper Analysis for Menganalisis dan Arti yang dalam film ''
IDENTIFIKASI NILAI PENDIDIKAN PADA KARAKTER UTAMA FILM ZOOTOPIA''

Abstrak

Background and Analysis

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengidentifikasi nilai-nilai pendidikan karakter pada tokoh utama Zootopia. Penelitian ini merupakan penelitian kualitatif deskriptif dimana pembacaan dekat digunakan untuk mengumpulkan data dari plot, cerita, dan setting film. Prosedur penelitian adalah mengalirkan, mengidentifikasi, menganalisis, dan menarik kesimpulan proses ini dapat diulang berkali-kali untuk memastikan data. Subjek penelitian ini adalah film dan pendidikan nilai-nilai karakter menjadi objek penelitian ini. Delapan belas nilai pendidikan karakter yang tertuang dalam keputusan Mendiknas) digunakan dalam penelitian ini. Tiga Belas nilai pendidikan karakter yang ditemukan dalam penelitian ini, nilai-nilai tersebut adalah kerja keras disiplin, tanggung jawab, kreatif, apresiatif, mandiri, damai, toleran, demokratis, patriotisme, nasionalisme, jujur, gemar membaca,. Dapat disimpulkan bahwa media seperti film juga dapat digunakan untuk mendidik anak dengan nilai-nilai pendidikan karakter.

Kata kunci: apresiatif, mandiri, damai, toleran, demokratis, patriotisme, nasionalisme, jujur, gemar membaca

CONCLUSION

From that description above, it could be seen that 13 values of character education are found on Judy Hopps's characterization as the main character of Zootopia. Those values are hardworking disciplined, responsible, creative, appreciative, autonomous, peaceful, tolerant, democratic, patriotism, nationalism, honesty, bibliophile. Some values are shown by Judy Hopps in the beginning until at the end of a story like hardworking, disciplined, responsible, creative, appreciative, democratic, patriotic, peaceful then the values that sometimes appeared in her characterization are friendly/communicative, especially in subcharacter of cooperating, tolerant, nationalism, and environmental awareness. Children who watch this film can learn character education values that can be seen in Judy Hopps.

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

yes it is available, I have made it for the question column and the information data

2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

My data is obtained through observation, documentation, participation and evaluation. because the journal that I make comes from the film. that's why I watch movies to make a journal, the title of the journal that I make is to identify the values of character education in the main character of Zootopia.

3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Yes, because the journal that I make is based on the source of the film I watch, and I watch it over and over again to find out the character of the film

4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

Yes, this makes a theoretical contribution to the development of science because it contains meaning and meaning regarding the value of patience and the value of persistence.

5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

Answer : No. This is not discussing the controversial issues that are currently going on, but rather discussing the deep meaning and meaning of a song and analyzing what values the song has.

6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

Answer : Yes, this problem requires an answer and an immediate solution because people need to know the deep meaning and significance of IDENTIFICATION OF EDUCATION VALUE ON THE MAIN CHARACTER OF THE ZOOTOPIA FILM

7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

Yes, the problems posed are still within the limits of the author's interest and ability

8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

Answer : The shift that occurs in the events in the journal is when someone tries to find a life. The value of determination and patience can be seen in this Hopps's characterization in character education is a hard worker who appears 26 times, from the beginning to the end of the film. The hardworking character can be divided into two sub-characters, namely persistent and committed. Judy Hopps points out that she's persistent for 20 times.

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

This is useful for the development of science and the wider community in the future because in the paper Boat song there are values that are worthy of imitation. Like the value of patience in waiting and looking for a life partner, then there is also the value of persistence in achieving your goals or dreams.

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Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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